

IN-SITU CONSOLIDATION OF PEEK COMPOSITES BY AUTOMATED PLACEMENT TECHNOLOGIES.

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ABSTRACT

Current aerospace primary structures such as wing skins are manufactured of metallic material or pre-impregnated fiber material with thermoset resin. In this later case, they are built by co-curing or co-bonding procedures with carbon/epoxy unidirectional tape (UD) in automatic tape laying fiber placement machines. Specific matrix as polyetheretherketone (PEEK), polyetherketoneketone (PEKK) or polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) can improved the performance to epoxies and the variety of matrix and fiber reinforcements offer optimal of composite structures solutions ribs, stiffeners, brackets, clips and cleats built with press-forming methods are good examples of the use of these materials in the new B787 and A350. Other examples are the leading edge of A380, rudder and elevators of Gulfstream G650 business jet and floors with riveted or welded beams.

FIDAMC has developed a thermoplastic fiber placement technology based on laser beam heating that will enable in-situ consolidation (ISC) of the thermoplastic material out of the autoclave. The aim of these processes is to avoid the use of autoclave and to reduce the number of processing steps, and consequently reduce the cost considerably, while maintaining competitive properties.

It is shown a novel in-situ consolidation and co-consolidation technology in order to manufacture, using automated technologies, thermoplastic (PEEK) composite parts with high level of integration. FIDAMC has been extensively researched, developed and validated this technology through the life of different Clean SKY (ISINTHER, JTI_CS-2011-1-ECO-01-021 and GRA (Green Regional Aircraft) 2014 and Spanish National projects as TARGET-CENIT Program 2010.

The unique equipment and process including real time temperature monitoring has resulted in components with 35-45% crystallinity and required degree of consolidation (DOC) not further heat vacuum bag for autoclave processing is needed. Basic properties have been obtained to fix the design allowable and a mature and robust co-consolidation manufacturing process validated through a real aircraft stiffened frame.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 State of art

The use of thermoplastic matrix in carbon fibre reinforced components has been growing continuously in automotive and aerospace applications. These composites are becoming the material of choice for replacing traditional metallic materials because higher strength to weight ratios, better chemical and impact resistance and design flexibility. The future market of thermoplastic components will increase through 2014 and beyond.

Besides thermoplastics have recognized aspects such as excellent Fire, Smoke, and Toxicity (FST) properties, higher mechanical properties and damage tolerance, chemical resistance, infinite shop life, weld ability of thermoplastic components, reuse of material and shorter manufacturing cycles compared to their competitor thermosets. Thermoplastic resins offer a high potential not only regarding material properties, but also in order to reduce processing, logistic, operation and life cycle costs.

Current aerospace primary structures such us wing skins are manufactured of metallic material or preimpregnated fiber material with thermoset. In this later case, they are built typically by co-curing or

co-bonding procedures with carbon/epoxy unidirectional tape in automatic tape laying or fibre placement machines.

Current thermoplastic composite parts are predominately processed with methods including stamp molding, thermoforming, autoclave molding, diaphragm forming, roll forming, filament winding and pultrusion and joining technologies such as electrical resistance, ultrasonic and induction welding, as figure 1 shows. These processing methods have some barriers for their large scale adoption in aircraft structures production:

1. Only limited size and geometry parts can be built by press and autoclave molding. For example, only flat and constant thickness long stringers.
2. High operational costs due to high energy consumption.
3. Conventional heating sources are not thermally effective and efficient.
4. High material and consumables usage because of manual bagging operation.
5. Most of them need post processing or two steps consolidation.
6. Only partial automation has been achieved.
7. High capital costs (e.g. autoclave, press...)

Figure1: Evolution technology level

The opportunity for thermoplastics is to approach to the automation of the lamination process with technologies such as a gas torch, infrared or laser as heating source added in automated tape placement.

In-situ consolidation processes currently are the main goal of most research and technology projects on thermoplastic materials. The aim of these processes is to avoid the use of autoclave and to reduce the number of processing steps, and consequently reduce the cost considerably, while maintaining competitive properties.

However, this rapid out of the autoclave thermoplastic composite processing technology has some limiting aspects for its commercial adoption in aircraft structures such as the ones proposed in this topic:

- Lack of proven data on materials and part performance with these new processing techniques.
- It is necessary to develop suitable process parameters and demonstrate their robustness in integral stiffened panels

2 AUTOMATED IN SITU LAY-UP AND CONSOLIDATION

The in-situ consolidation and lamination of thermoplastic process is a recent development of automated manufacturing and this technology has been extensively researched by FIDAMC in the following experiences described next:

- Clean Sky Project “ISINTHER”- GA n°: 296549: FIDAMC was the coordinator of this project which goal was to get a reliable automatic industrial process based on ATL manufacturing technique for the in-situ consolidation of thermoplastic composites. FIDAMC developed thermoplastic composite panels and novel composite structures configuration with co-consolidation methodologies for the stringers to skin joints.
- In “TARGET” (Spanish project funded by the Industry and Innovation ministry- CENIT Programme), FIDAMC has researched on automated placement technologies for thermoplastic material with laser heating source. Main process parameters to manufacture flat panels were obtained.
- In “ICARO” (Spanish project funded by the Industry and Innovation ministry- CENIT Programme), thermoplastic composite panels and novel composite structures configuration and methodologies were developed.
- In Clean Sky GRA 2014 ITD with EADS CASA E9737639 the intent was to present a novel in-situ consolidation and co-consolidation technology in order to manufacture, using automated technologies, thermoplastic (PEEK) composite parts with high level of integration. These cabin frames are currently being tested in EADS CASA facilities.

The principle is the tape is in-situ joined and bonded to the substrate with the aid of a laser source and applies pressure through rollers.

2.1 Machine description

Machine shown in figure 2 consists in a heated head that incorporates a process to melt, deposit and freeze the thermoplastic unidirectional tapes, ply by ply on a mandrel tool. The process requires a continuous heating source, which is designed to ensure the controllability, high efficiency and temperature. An infrared camera is incorporated to the head to measure the temperature at the focal spot in the contact with roller (NIP) and length in the substrate and adjust the power and the angle of the laser optics.

Figure 2: Thermoplastic machine description

The process requires continuous and consistent heating in order to bond the polymer surfaces and also requires overcoming other issues of the different mechanisms involved in this technology such as intimate contact, molecular diffusion and consolidation. For that purpose, due to its high energy, controllability and high efficiency, the machine integrates a variable optic diode type laser as heating source. The scanner enables optimum distribution of radiation between incoming tape and substrate

and optimum processing profile of temperatures along the lamination. Besides the heat source, other components of the machine head include an on line consolidation roller, a movable layup system and control devices. Both incoming tape and substrate are consolidated by the action of the consolidation roller under controlled heat and pressure. Finally under pressure of a second roller, the microstructure is frozen in a cold area to lower temperature under crystallization point to reach adequate mechanical properties.

2.2 Process parameters

The parameters optimization was conducted by the methodology shown in figure 3, with a study on mechanical and physical properties of in-situ consolidation of laminate. The evaluation of this result was compared to specimens built in autoclave or hot plate press.

Wedge peeling tests were chosen for laser adjustment in order to control the heat distribution between substrate, feeding tape and laser power control to enable the desired temperature profile and thermal history during lamination.

The variables to be controlled and improved during the process to achieve enough consolidation were the lamination speed, temperature and thermal history and pressure. The system of pressure was modified throughout the time, from metallic heated rollers until rubber rollers or using only one roller or a system of two independent rollers. The critical issue in the consolidation is to support the temperature necessary for the process a certain time. Laser profiles and velocity of the system establish the thermal history of the material. The velocity is direct related with the exposure time of the material to temperature, and with the heat transfer through the whole laminate.

The process parameters optimization methodology it was conducted by varying one process parameters while keeping the sensing parameters constant. Standard In-plane Shear Strength tests (IPSS) were used to assess the final DOC in comparison with autoclaved samples because is the dominating factor in the matrix-interface performance.

Figure 3: Methodology graph

Evaluation of mechanical performance of specimens lead the most influence is the placement speed and the thermal history: the more time at temperature higher than melting point during lamination, higher is the degree of consolidation.

The maximum placement velocity is limited by the time required to achieve intimate contact.

When we have increased the intimate contact and temperature for the same velocity, best mechanical properties are achieved in the in situ consolidation process. Figure 4 exhibits a summary of the effect of the thermal history during laminating and the best performance is obtained with the incorporation of a second laser between rollers.

Figure 4: Evolution of IPSS properties with ISC process

2.3 Material

The material used in this work was Cytec APC2/AS4, which consists of a carbon fiber UD tape reinforced PEEK pre-impregnated material and its characteristics are 6.2mm (1/4'') wide and 0.135mm of nominal thickness. The quality of the unidirectional tapes ("slit tapes") is other of the critical parameter besides of processing properties; it has special impact in shear properties. The current material shows some issues in the associated parameters affecting the final quality of the laminates such as lack of resin in the surface, smoothness, distribution of resin fiber and thickness variation. This material requires a very low intraply void content. Furthermore, it is critical a fibre/resin uniformity homogeneity besides a uniform thickness shape. The "slit tape" must have a very low thickness variation in the tow (less than 5%). An uniform fiber/resin distribution, surface resin content equal to one filament diameter, thickness variation less than 6% across the entire tape width and void content less than 1% are the minimum requirements that must fulfill an in-situ consolidation grade material called "flat material" as is shown in figure 5.

Figure 5: Detail of raw material of APC2/AS4 and flat material supplied by Cytec

3 CO-CONSOLIDATION OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES BY AUTOMATED IN-SITU LAY-UP

Both demonstrators, ISINTHER and GRA frames, consist in complex structures using thermoplastic of high strength CF/PEEK. FIDAMC has been capable of manufacturing thermoplastic composite parts with high level of integration of stringers and spars by co-consolidation methodology, fusing together multiple preforms in a single melting step. Technological demos of integrated hollow hat stiffeners panels have been built showing the feasibility of joining the stringers and the skin.

Thermoplastic in situ consolidation process and co-consolidation of stringers in a single step allows removing autoclave cycle and ancillary materials such as vacuum bags, and therefore, reducing production time and energy consumption. Continuous stringer forming also contributes to reduce manufacturing lead time and allows long stringer profiles manufacturing with thermoplastic resins.

The main drivers are:

- To assess an in situ consolidation process for thermoplastic material orientated to industrial outcome.
- To apply the main guidelines from above for trials and stiffened panels demonstrators.
- To assess the potential benefit impact of the in situ consolidation thermoplastic process in terms of environment, production costs, higher chemical/mechanical properties for structural design and elongated life cycle.

Finally, demonstrators were built to study manufacturability issues applying the optimum parameters set for the in-situ placement process with the flat laminates of previous stage. During the project development, FIDAMC has made an important effort to design and manufacture two different tooling, to carry out integration test to develop the thermoplastic bonding method for the automatic in-situ co-consolidation manufacturing process.

Modular tooling geometry enables easy and accurate placement and handling of the omega-shape stringers allowing carry out controlled and reliable integration process accordingly to aerospace requirements as well as to industrial applicability of their manufacturing processes.

To be able to manufacturing the demonstrator, it was necessary to solve some problems related with the manufacturing:

- A) Manufacturing stringer by press forming
- B) Skin first ply deposition.
- C) Surface treatments.

3.1 ISINTHER Demonstrator design and tooling

Feasibility demonstrator has a flat skin of 600 mm length and 600 mm width and two omega section stringers with stacking: $((0/90/+45/-45)_s)_s$ and nominal thickness of 2.1mm. The basic skin has stacking sequence of $((90/0/-45/+45)_s)_s$ and same nominal thickness than stringers. See figure 6.

Figure 6: Configuration of feasibility demonstrator

The consolidating tooling allows joining the consolidated hollow hat stringers placed in the holes of the molds and the lamination and co-consolidation of skin above them as is shown in Figure 7. The tool has incorporated vacuum system to enable the lamination and thermally isolated to assure an

optimum heat transfer to get the thermal history of the thermoplastic material.

Figure 7: Co-consolidation tooling

3.2 ISINTHER demonstrator manufacturing

The manufacturing process of the stiffened panel under consideration is divided in three distinct stages:

1. Stiffener flat lamination by automated in-situ consolidation.
2. Thermo-formed stiffener by press thermoforming.
3. Flat panel lamination on the stringer flanges, performing panel manufacturing and stringer integration in one step (in-situ consolidation).

The figure 8 shows the complete manufacturing steps.

Figure 8: ISHINTER demonstrator manufacturing

3.3 GRA FRAMES Demonstrator manufacturing

Finally, the last demonstrator combines the advantages of the in-situ consolidation with laser heating source on integrated structures with the thermoforming technology. This fully integrated component with skin, stiffeners and spar is produced in only one shot by co-consolidation methodology and is representative of a cockpit frame assembled in the structural cockpit demonstrator of the regional aircraft of Airbus Defense and Space for the structure test campaign at facilities. The

demonstrator comprises a step forward in the feasibility of the thermoplastic development including lamination strategies with flat skins with local reinforcements, pad-ups, ply drop-off and final integration of stiffeners and spars working on the principles learnt in previous ISINTHER activities.

The manufacturing steps and tooling details are shown in figure 9.

Figure 9: GRA frames manufacturing

4 CONCLUSIONS

FIDAMC has developed technology which enables the automated layup and in situ consolidation of carbon fiber reinforced PEEK. The unique equipment and process including real time temperature monitoring has resulted in components with 35-45% crystallinity in the matrix and required DOC not further heat vacuum bag for autoclave processing/oven is needed. Basic properties have been obtained to fix the design allowable and a mature and robust co-consolidation manufacturing process validated through a real aircraft stiffened frame. The knowledge achieved with those activities will be used in future projects win in recently launched Clean Sky 2.

The evolution of the thermoplastic head from 2011 and the achievements in technology and structures are shown in figure 10.

Figure 10: Evolution of thermoplastic machine head

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